

Aquaculture, Disease Occurrence and Preventive Strategies in Mymensingh District

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Suggested Citation

Nahar, S., Rahman, M.H., Alam, M.A., Ashaf-Ud-Doulah., M., Nisheeth, N.N., & Meem, A.A. (2024). Aquaculture, Disease Occurrence, and Preventive Strategies in Mymensingh District. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 700-710. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).62](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).62)

Abstract:

The study was conducted to assess the current fish culture strategy and management techniques in two upazilas (Trishal and Muktagacha) in Mymensingh district. The results revealed that the average pond area in Trishal ranged from 100 to 1500 decimal. However, the average pond area in Muktagacha was higher by 200-4000 decimal. The farmers in the study area used monoculture (50%). One-third (33.33%) preferred polyculture, with a few (16.67%) following both culture systems. The studied farms used preventive measures such as frequent health checks (66.67%), pond drying (66.67%), and pond lime application (100%). Approximately 66.67%

of farmers used probiotics in their fields for beneficial purposes such as water quality control, growth augmentation, and disease resistance. In each selected upazila of Mymensingh district, 87.5% of farmers acclimatized fry before stocking them into ponds. The data revealed that fish production varied according to culture type, location, and culture duration. Trishal had the highest average yield (158.5 kg/ decimal). The average production in Muktagacha was (143.5kg/decimal). The results showed that Trishal had the largest year-round Pangas production (245kg/decimal) and Muktagachha had the lowest (150kg/decimal). Results regarding the disease and health assessment of cultured ponds evolved that four (04) types of diseases were discovered in the study area: bacterial, viral, fungal, and protozoan diseases. Most farmers performed preventive measures such as regular fish health inspections, pond drying, lime application, pond weeding, water turbidity removal, water addition, and so on. Almost all farmers (100%) in the specified area use lime in their ponds, while 41.67% undertake aquatic weed control.

Keywords: *Culture pattern, Diseases, Preventive Measures.*

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Introduction

Fish health has been a top concern for aquaculturists as aquaculture practices have become more intense and commercialized. One of the most promising and rapidly growing food-producing industries in the world, aquaculture has the greatest potential to meet the rising demand for aquatic food. Over the past few years, aquaculture has expanded significantly worldwide and grown to be an important economic sector. Diseases and the degradation of environmental conditions are significant issues in fish farming that result in significant financial losses due to the increasing commercialization and intensification of aquaculture operations. The most well-known method for addressing the prevalence of bacterial diseases in aquaculture was through the administration of antibiotics. The indiscriminate use of these antibiotics for maintaining bacterial infection has been accountable for the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, that has significant effect on the reduction of the efficiency of a treatment option and may be liable for long term unpleasant impacts in the aquaculture environment such as accumulation of those antibiotics in fish body tissues, reduction of beneficial microbiota and immune suppression of fish. Among all of the mentioned unpleasant impacts, the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria has paid more attention globally. The development of an eco-friendly, non-antibiotic agent is seen to be one of the essential elements for appropriate aquaculture health management because of the risks associated with the use of antibiotics. An effective biosecurity policy for a fish or shellfish aquaculture enterprise would include disease prevention, disease monitoring, cleaning and disinfection in between production cycles, and generalized safety measures (Smith, 2012; Rahman *et al.* 2024).

Aquaculture industry is promoting overall fish production in Bangladesh but facing problems of water pollution and disease outbreaks. The parasites and other factors such as environmental stress, nutritional deficiency etc.

are mainly responsible for the disease outbreaks of fish and have caused significant economic losses. Potential economic losses from disease outbreaks are significant, and can affect the survival of the industry. In order to prevent disastrous epidemics of infectious organisms in aqua farms, an adoptive approach to disease management needs to be followed. The total area of Mymensingh district is 4363.48 km². Some upazilas under this district including Mymensingh Sadar, Trishal, Muktagachha, Tarakanda, Fulbaria, Ishwarganj, Gouripur etc. are rich in huge number of hatcheries and farms. Many people are involved in commercial fishing and contribute a major role in the food sector. Sultana (2001) reported that 92% of the pond owners wanted to culture fish and all of them were in favor of carp culture. Most farmers (64.15%) are interested on polyculture than monoculture because of high production. This has been possible due to enormous natural water bodies in the form of pond, reservoir, canal, river, beels etc. and also the support of government and non-government organizations (Rahman, 2005).

Biosecurity requires the adoption of a set of attitudes and behaviors by people to reduce risk in all activities involving domestic, captive exotic and wild birds and their products. Disease causing organisms are often spread by people or equipment. Biosecurity measures reduce the risk of exposing farmed animals to disease causing organisms by preventing the spread of disease organisms onto and off a farm and preventing the spread of disease organisms within a farm.

Probiotics have been proven to be positive promoters of aquatic animal growth, survival and health. In aquaculture, intestines, gills, the skin mucus of aquatic animals, and habitats or even culture collections and commercial products, can be sources for acquiring appropriate probiotics, which have been identified as bacteria (Gram-positive and Gram-negative) and non-bacteria (bacteriophages, microalgae and yeasts). The research of probiotics for aquatic animals is increasing with the demand for environment-friendly

aquaculture. Some commercial products are referred to as probiotics, though they were designed to treat the rearing medium, not to supplement the diet.

Given the circumstances, a thorough assessment is supposed to be carried out in a few selected regions of Mymensingh district in order to ascertain and contrast the state of current aquafarm culture and management practices in order to comprehend the best means of ensuring the farmed fish production. The current study will make it possible to identify the issues surround fish farms and the ensuing mitigation strategies to improve the fish production of commercial fish farms in the district of Mymensingh.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Field data on the status of fish farming, production, occurrence of disease, farm biosecurity, using concept about probiotics and overall fish health management strategy were collected for a period of time through questionnaire survey from twenty-four (24) aquafarms of two Upazilas of Mymensingh district i.e., Muktagacha, and Trishal. Necessary data were collected from fish farmers by frequent field visits and interviews.

Selection of Fish Farms

Three farmers from each of two upazilas were selected after successful discussions with the Upazila Fisheries Officer, some commercial feed and animal health medicine company Officers. Total 24 farms were selected from Muktagacha and Trishal under Mymensingh District.

Data Collection Method

A set of questions was organized in a sequential and required logical format to collect the data. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) tool including Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was conducted with fish farmers. Cross-check

interviews were conducted with key informant such as District Fisheries Officer, Upazila Fisheries Officer, different commercial feed company officer and animal health company officer working here in Mymensingh district.

Prior to field survey, background information on the number, location and distribution of fish farms and aquaculture activities were collected. Data collection method was divided into four steps i.e., questionnaire interviews, focus group discussion, cross-check interviews with key informants and observations of locations.

Questionnaire Interviews

The questionnaire had been divided into several sections. The first section focused on general farming and farmer's personal information, the second section on stocking and pond management information, the third section covered the information on biosecurity issues and the final section focused on fish health and disease problems, their management interventions used to control disease.

Focus Group Discussion

Information from fish farmers were collected through focus group discussion. FGD was conducted to get an overview of fish farming activities in the study area.

Cross Check Interviews with Key Informants

Cross check, interviews were conducted with key informants such as Senior Upazila Fisheries Officer, Upazila Fisheries Officer and different commercial feed and medicine company officer working in Mymensingh district, where information was contradictory or requested for further assessment.

Observation of the Locations

Besides interview, some required information was collected by direct observation including nature of the culture ponds, culture species, biosecurity issues, farming activities and harvesting and marketing system of fish etc. The photographs cover the physical features of the study areas.

Statistical Analysis

All collected data were analyzed using “Microsoft Excel 2019”. The summary tables were prepared to fulfill the objectives of this study. The results were shown in descriptive tabular and graphical presentation.

Results

Pond Area and Depth

The average pond area was ranged between 100 to 1500 decimal in Trishal. However average pond area was comparatively higher in Muktagacha within 200-4000 decimal. In contrast, the highest average pond depth was 173.75 cm in Trishal followed by 147.5 cm in Muktagacha Upazila (Table 1).

Table 1. Pond Area Selected Upazila of Mymensingh District

Description	Pond area of selected upazila of Mymensingh district	
	Muktagacha	Trishal
Area(dm)	200-4000	100-1500
Avg. area (dm)	2100	800
Depth(cm)	77-218	127.5-220

Types of Culture

Both polyculture and monoculture systems were practiced in all of the selected Upazila. From the data, it was observed that most of the farmers of the study area adopted monoculture (50%). Whereas, one-third (33.33%) of them preferred polyculture and a few (16.67%) followed both the culture systems.

Pre-Stocking Management

Farmers prepared their ponds thorough pond drying (66.67%), pond mud removal (75%), undesirable species removal (100%), repairing

pond embankment repair (83.33%), aquatic weeds removal (83.33%), liming (100%) and fertilization (16.67%) (Table 2). The percentages of different measures of pond management were more or less same in all the selected areas. In case of pond mud removal and same on embankment repairing, there was a noticeable difference seen between Muktagachha and Trishl because of comparatively bigger pond area and very often removal of pond mud due to high expenditure. In some areas farmers did not use fertilizer since they used medicine for creating suitable environment especially for enhancing phytoplankton and zooplankton growth.

Table 2. Pre-Stocking Management in Selected Upazila of Mymensingh District

Measures usually taken before stocking of fish fry	Respondent		Total farmers	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
	Yes	No			
Pond preparation	24	0	24	100	0
Pond drying	16	8		66.67	33.33
Pond mud removal	18	6		75	25
Undesirable species removal	24	0		100	0
Pond embankment repair	20	4		83.33	16.67
Aquatic weeds removal	20	4		83.33	16.67
Liming	24	0		100	0
Fertilization	4	20		16.67	83.33

Stocking and Management of Fry

It was observed that 87.5% farmer’s stocked diseased free fry in the survey areas. They tried to collect the fry from renowned hatcheries to

avoid diseased fry and any other problems. 87.5% farmers acclimatized fry before stocking into the ponds at each selected upazila of

Mymensingh district. It was observed that there were no quarantine facilities in any farms.

Feed Preference for Fish

Farmers were asked either they preferred farm-made feed or commercial feed for cultured

fishes. Around 16.67% farmers preferred farm-made feed for fish. On the other hand, almost all the farmers (83.33%) preferred commercial feed (Table 3).

Table 3. Preference of Feed for Fish

Feed Type	Muktagacha		Trishal	
	No. of farmers	(%)	No. of farmers	(%)
Farm made	0	0	2	25
Commercial	8	100	6	75
Total	8	100	8	100

Fish Production

In the selected area, Pangas, Tilapia, Koi, Shing, Pabda and Carps were cultured in studied farms either by monoculture system or by polyculture system. Polyculture with Tilapia/Pangas/Koi were mostly productive than monoculture system. Data showed that fish production was varied with culture types, areas, and culture period. The highest average production was in Trishal (158.5Kg/decimal). Whereas, the average production in Muktagacha was (143.5kg/decimal). It was found that, the year-

round production of Pangas was highest in Trishal 245kg/decimal and lowest (150kg/decimal) in Muktagachha. The Koi production in Muktagachha was higher (160kg/decimal) than Trishal (127.5kg/decimal). Tilapia production data showed the best production (67.5kg/decimal) in Muktagacha, whereas the comparatively lowest found (65kg/decimal) in Trishal. Shing production was highest (205kg/decimal) in Muktagacha where less (115kg/decimal) was in Trishal (Table 4).

Table 4. Average Production (kg/decimal) in Selected Upazilas of Mymensingh District

Culture species	Muktagacha		Trishal	
	Range	Avg.	Range	Avg.
Shing	200-210	205	110-120	115
Pangas	140-160	150	200-290	245
Koi	150-170	160	125-130	127.5
Tilapia	65-70	67.5	60-70	65
Avg. production		143.5		158.5

Water Management of the Farms

It was observed that the farmers were conscious about the water sources. They knew that contaminated water sources are very harmful for their farm fishes. There were 91.67% farmers used ground water by using pump. Farmers were

asked if they measure water quality parameters of their farms including temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH range, alkalinity, ammonia and others. Among them every farmer (100%) measured pH while 8.33% and 91.67% measured alkalinity and ammonia respectively (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Farmers Measure Water Quality Parameters in Mymensingh District

Removal of pond waste

In selected Upazila of Mymensingh, 75% farmers removed pond bottom waste and dried their culture ponds after two or three cycle of production.

Disinfection of Transport Equipment

After harvesting, farmers used plastic baskets, aluminum pots, plastic drums etc. to transport the fishes to the market by transporting vehicles like manual van, pickup truck, lorry etc. There was no farmer use disinfected the transport equipment.

Facility of Sprays, Footbaths to Disinfect Boots and Vehicles

There was no facility of sprays, footbath to disinfect boots and vehicles like van, truck, lorry

etc. before entering into the facilities. Farmers did not follow this biosecurity program.

Health Status Checking of Fish

There were some differences found among the selected upazila on the basis of monitoring fish health. It was found that all (100%) the farmers monitored the health condition of fishes in their ponds. The 12.5% of the farmers in both upazilas monitored the farms on daily basis, while 37.5% farmers in Muktagacha and 25% farmers monitored the disease condition weekly, respectively. On the other hand, 50% and 62.5% farmers monitored the health condition on bi-weekly basis, respectively (Table 5).

Table 5. Monitoring Fish Health by Farmers of Study Areas

Criteria	Muktagacha	Trishal
	n=24	n=24
Daily	12.5%	12.5%
Weekly	37.5%	25%
Bi-weekly	50%	62.5%

Disease and Health Analysis of Cultured Ponds

Data regarding the disease and health analysis of cultured ponds showed that there were four different types of diseases found in the study

area including bacterial, viral, fungal and protozoan diseases. These diseases further categorized as low, medium, highly and not concerned of the farmers. The whole data is represented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Status of Type of Diseases Preventive Measures

Preventive Measures

Most of the farmers took some preventive measures such as regular fish health checking, pond drying, application of lime, weeding the pond, removing water turbidity, addition of water etc. Almost all the farmers (100%) in the

selected area, always apply lime in their pond. About 0% farmers in the study area took measures to remove water turbidity where 58.34% farmers always added water into the pond. Controlling aquatic weed was practiced always by 41.67% farmers (Table 6).

Table 6. Preventive Measures Took by the Farmers of Two Upazila (n=24)

Measures practiced	Average farmers response		
	Never	Usual	Always
Regular fish health checking	0%	33.33%	66.67%
Pond drying	8.33%	25%	66.67%
Application of lime	0%	0%	100%
Weeding the pond	16.66%	41.67%	41.67%
Removing water turbidity	100%	0%	0%
Addition of water	33.33%	8.33%	58.34%
Other	100%	0%	0%

Figure 3. Types of Probiotics Used in Mymensingh District

Use of Probiotics

Among the participants only 33.33% farm owners used probiotics in the pond for beneficial purposes where 25% of farms used water quality regulatory probiotics, 25% of farms used soil probiotics and 8.33% used gut probiotics (Fig. 3).

During the study period the growth performance was comparatively high by deducting feed cost, labor cost and overall maintenance cost where the overall production was high. The data showed that the production increased by 4-5% after applying probiotics.

Aqua Drugs Used for Water Quality Management

A variety of aqua drugs have been utilised at various points throughout the process of preparing fish ponds and improving the overall water quality. For the purpose of maintaining the quality of the water, such products as Bioaqua, Zeolite, Hunter, Zeolite Gold, Mega Zeo, Geotox, Urea, Aquakleen, Lime, Bio Aqua-50, Biomin, Aquaboost, Blue vitriol, Polgard+, Benthod, Ammonil, Biomin Pond Life, Gastrap, TSP, Aqualite, Aqua Pure, Matrix, Pond Life, and Zeo Prime were reported to be applied.

Aqua Drugs Used to Improve Dissolve Oxygen Level

The several aqua drugs and chemicals were reported to be used to improve the oxygen concentration within the culture unit, such as Oxy more, Oxygen plus, Oxylife, Oxy-Ren, Oxy gold, Aqua oxygen, Oxy-A, ACI-OX, Bio Care, Bio- Ox, Oxy-Gold, Oxy-A, Oxyflow, Oxypond, and Oxymax were some of the treatments that were used within the research region so that the level of dissolved oxygen could be increased.

Aqua Drugs Used as Growth Promoter

A variety of aquatic drugs were reported to be applied to promote the growth performance and to enhance production. A number of drugs and chemicals, such as Aqua bind, Nutrimax, Prottox aqua, Safegut, Aquazyme, Megavit-Aqua, E-Vet Plus, Aqua Boost, Aqua-C, Square Aquamix

powder, Cevit-Aqua, Acimix super fish, CP-Vet WSP, Aquamin, Acimix, Super-fish, Square Aquamix, Panvit-Aqua, Rena C, Rena Fish, Vitamix F-Aqua, Rena-WS, Charger Gel, Bio-Permixon (Gold), Vitax-C, Vitax-ES, Timsen, Aeon Fish Grower, AQ Grow-P, Vitamix F Aqua, and Provit Gel, were found to be used in the study area.

Antibiotics Used for Fish Disease Treatment

For the treatment of a variety of diseases, the majority of farmers applied a number of different drugs i.e., Formalin, Tetravet WSP, Moxilin Vet WSP, Oxy-D Vet, Aquamycine, Oxy-Dox-F100, Captor, Doxy-A Vet WSP, Renamox 15%-vet, Acimox (vet) Powder, Cipro-A vet, and Ciproflox.

Aqua Drugs Used as Disinfectant

Disinfectants are frequently used throughout different areas of aquaculture. These tools are primarily used for the purpose of disinfecting hatchery facilities and other related equipment. A variety of disinfectants, including Polgard Plus, Ossi C, Virex, Bleaching powder, Timsen, Micronil, Pathonil, Germnil, Povidon aqua, Bactrisol, Aqua cleaning plus, Eraprim vet, GPC-8, Aquaxide plus, and Povicef, were used for disinfection purposes. Chemical disinfectants were employed by farmers to maintain pathogen-free conditions in their ponds.

Discussion

The goal of this study was to learn more about the existing pattern of commercial fish farms of the Mymensingh District. The commercial farmers lacked a thorough understanding of biosecurity procedures. Only a few commercial fish farms were found to be enclosed by fences, whereas the majority of the farms were not. As a result, the most common occurrence in the research region was wild animal entrances, which could be sources of pathogens for disease outbreaks in the farms.

No farm was discovered to have foot bath facilities prior to entering their premises or to provide protective clothes for their own

employees or visitors. In the instance of fish hatchery biosecurity, Faruk *et al.* (2012) obtained comparable results. Except for a few well-established large-scale fish farms in the research area, most of the farms were found to lack sanitary toilet facilities. It was discovered that the majority of farmers do not have a bin to store empty packets or pots. Many farmers throw away the empty packets or pots after utilizing medications or other materials in the ponds, thereby deteriorating the farm environment.

According to Yanong and Erlacher (2012), it is critical to prevent predators or pests from entering farms since they can spread disease to other farms. In aquaculture farms, birds are key predators or pests. It's been proven that birds can spread bacteria and viruses through their droppings.

Due to their smaller size than Pangas farms, tilapia and Koi farms were shown to have less potential to introduce pollutants into ponds, since the farmers adequately prepared pond dikes. Most Pangas farms have the potential to introduce pollutants via surface run-off from industrial, domestic, and agricultural sources, particularly those that were converted from beels. Biosecurity is easier to establish in small, intensive, and regulated farming systems than in outdoor and large-scale operations, according to Horowitz & Horowitz (2003).

For the biosecurity program of an aqua farm, it is necessary to collect and stock disease-free fry. The majority of farmers stocked disease-free fry in their farm ponds, according to the findings of this study. Santahar, Adamdighi, and Bogura were the most common places from where farmers collected Pangas fry/fingerling. They used to get Tilapia and Koi fingerlings from government and private hatcheries in Mymensingh, as well as some local nurseries. Farmers have attempted to generate Pangas spawn in their own hatcheries, but the results have been disappointing. The farmers suspected that the soil quality and other criteria in the Mymensingh region were not ideal for generating Pangas spawn, but the causes of failure were unknown.

Almost all of the farmers used commercial pelleted feed purchased from various fish feed farms, and the majority of the commercial farms had good feed storage facilities and attempted to maintain correct storage conditions. The fish producers in this study found that keeping records was not a frequent practice. Most farmers kept a basic record of fry prices, transportation costs, labor costs, feeding costs, medicine use, netting and harvesting costs, selling prices, and income, among other things. Faruk *et al.* (2012) & Rahman *et al.* (2024) found similar results when looking at the biosecurity of fish hatcheries.

The majority of Pangas producers likewise eliminated their pond trash every three years. Some Pangas farms were so large that removing bottom waste was difficult, if not impossible. Because of the large volume of bottom decomposed mud, the water quality often worsened, weakening the fish and making them prone to disease. Smith (2012) stated that an important area of disease prevention and control that is often overlooked in the aquaculture industry is disinfection. Routine disinfection is used to reduce the pathogen load in a facility, thereby reducing the risk of spreading an infectious organism between groups of fish or shellfish in a single facility.

The majority of farmers were found not to disinfect their transport equipment, such as plastic baskets and aluminum pots, as well as their transport vehicles, such as manual vans, pickup vans, and trucks. According to Winton (2002), Ahmed *et al.* (2015) & Bari *et al.* (2024), before using equipment anywhere on or off the farm, it must be cleaned, disinfected, and dried for the best outcomes in destroying microorganisms.

A few farmers were found to be using various sorts of antibiotics and pesticides to control infections, according to the report. Antibiotics such as Ciprofloxacin, Tetracycline, Oxytetracycline, and chemicals like Zeolite, Bleaching Powder, Phostoxin, Rotenone, and others were used. Farmers are unaware of the long-term effects of these synthetic medications, according to Faruk *et al.* (2008).

Chemical costs were found to be the most expensive, accounting for 25.77% percent of overall costs in the Noakhali district, according to Shohel (1998). Lack of understanding about chemical use, suitable dose, application method, and indiscriminate chemical use were all recognized as concerns in the study. Therefore, farmers could be suggested to take some preventive measures at the beginning of the winter season which includes application of lime and salt, disinfecting of equipment, addition of water etc. (Faruk *et al.*, 2004).

Most studies concerned with the effects of probiotics on cultured aquatic animals and emphasized a reduction in mortality or conversely, increased survival (Chang and Liu, 2002), improved resistance against diseases (Lee and Bullis, 2003; Brown and Brooks, 2002) enhanced ability of beneficial microbes to adhere and colonize in the gut to antagonize harmful organisms (Islam, 2018) and to produce polyamines and digestive enzymes (Lightner, 2003 and Pietrak *et al.*, 2010). Farmers did not receive adequate disease control and health management methods from non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and government extension workers, according to the current study (GEOs).

In summary, from this study it was found that a few (16.67%) followed both the culture systems. Preventive measures such as regular health checking (66.67%), drying of pond (66.67%) and applying lime in the pond (100%) were practiced in the studied farms. About 66.67% farmers used probiotics in their farms for beneficial purposes like water quality management, growth enhancement and disease resistance. 87.5% farmers acclimatized fry before stocking into the ponds at each selected upazila of Mymensingh district. Almost all the farmers (100%) in the selected area, always apply lime in their pond and controlling of aquatic weed was found to be practiced by 41.67% farmers.

Conclusions

Investigating the sustainability of fish culture and the ensuing health management strategies

on multiple farms in the Mymensingh district was the aim of this study. Most of them knew very little about biosecurity matters. Good biosecurity practices are essential to keeping fish healthy and reducing the risk of disease transmission in aqua farms. The principles of biosecurity should be better understood by commercial farmers, and they should be encouraged to properly implement biosecurity programs on their farms. To raise fish farms' overall biosecurity status, it is suggested that current fish farming practices be improved through organizational and institutional approaches.

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